

Niementowski-4-Ketoquinazoline Synthesis : Part III. Study of the Condensation of N-Acyl-Anthranilic Acids with Formamide, Urethane and Urea

H. J. Mehta, V. S. Patel and S. R. Patel

The condensations of 4- and 5-nitro-N-acetylanthranilic acids with formamide and those of the unsubstituted and 4- and 5-chloro and nitrosubstituted-N-acetyl and N-benzoylanthranilic acids with urethane and urea have been studied.

The results of the study of the application of the modified Niementowski-4-ketoquinazoline synthesis to the unsubstituted and chlorine substituted-N-acetylanthranilic acids have been reported and correlated in terms of the proposed reaction mechanism in the earlier communications⁽¹⁾. The present communication deals with the study of the application of the modified Niementowski-4-ketoquinazoline synthesis⁽¹⁾ to 4- and 5-nitro-N-acetyl and N-acylanthranilic acids and the study of the applicability of urethane and urea as reagents in place of formamide in the modified Niementowski-4-ketoquinazoline synthesis.

The condensation of 4-nitro-N-acetylanthranilic acid with formamide afforded a mixture of 7-nitro-2-methyl-3(H) (I) and 2(H)-3(H) (II) 4-ketoquinazolines. The nature of the product was revealed by the comparative UV spectral study of the reaction-product and the pure components of the product. The variations in the reaction-conditions with regard to the reaction-temperature and the relative proportions of the reactants did not bring about any change in the nature of the product. It was, however, found that the condensation of 4-nitro-N-acetylanthranilic-acid with acetamide afforded 7-nitro-2-methyl-3(H)-4-ketoquinazoline in about 50% yield. The condensation of 5-nitro-N-acetylanthranilic acid with

formamide also afforded a mixture of 6-nitro-2-methyl-3(H) (III) and 2(H)-3(H) (IV) 4-ketoquinazolines while its condensation with acetamide afforded the expected product (III) in about 50% yield. As reported in preceding communications, the condensations of simple and 4- and 5-chloro-N-acetylanthranilic acids with formamide afforded the corresponding bz-unsubstituted and 7- and 6-chloro-2-methyl-3(H)-4-ketoquinazolines respectively in excellent yields⁽¹⁾.

1. V. S. Patel and S. R. Patel, *This Journal*, 1965, **42**, 531; *ibid.*, 1967, **45**, 197.

The condensations of 4- and 5-nitro-N-benzoyl, N-*p*-nitrobenzoyl and N-*p*-anisoylanthranilic acids with formamide at about 180–85° afforded the corresponding 7- and 6-nitro-2-aryl-3(H)-4-ketoquinazolines respectively in yields ranging around 60%. It may be interesting to note that 5- and 4-nitroanthranilic acids on condensation with benzamide at about 180–85° afforded 6- and 7-nitro-2-phenyl-3(H)-4-ketoquinazoline in very poor yields. Thus the modified Niementowski-4-ketoquinazoline has proved superior to the original synthesis in this series also. According to the proposed reaction mechanism for the Niementowski-4-ketoquinazoline formamide is supposed to bring about the transformation of N-acylanthranilic

acid into the corresponding N-acylanthranilamide. In the original synthesis, this role is played by the much less reactive aroylamide. The N-acylanthranilamide then undergoes a subsequent facile cyclodehydration reaction affording the corresponding 2(R)-3(H)-4-ketoquinazoline⁽¹⁾.

With a view to study whether or not urethane and urea can play the role of formamide in the modified Niementowski-4-ketoquinazoline synthesis, the study of the condensation reactions of urethane and of urea with various N-acylanthranilic acids was undertaken. The condensation of N-acetyl anthranilic acid with urethane afforded 2-methyl-3(H)-4-ketoquinazoline in 53 and 74% yield when the reaction was carried out at 180° and 220° respectively. 6- and 7-chloro-2-methyl and 2-Ph-3(H)-4-ketoquinazolines were formed on condensing 5- and 4-chloro-N-acetyl and N-benzoylanthranilic acids respectively with urethane at 180–5°; the yields of the products in these reactions were found to be comparable to those reported by Patel and Patel for the same compounds formed on condensation of the corresponding N-acylanthranilic acid derivatives with formamide⁽¹⁾. The condensations of 4- and 5-nitro-N-acetylanthranilic acids with urethane yielded 7- and 6-nitro-2-methyl-3(H)-4-ketoquinazolines. The condensation of 4- and 5-nitro-N-benzoylanthranilic acids with urethane afforded 7- and 6-nitro-2-phenyl-3(H)-4-ketoquinazolines in good yields. These results indicate that urethane can be used as a reagent in place of formamide in the modified Niementowski-4-ketoquinazoline synthesis, and as can be judged from the comparative study of the yield of the final products formed on condensation of the corresponding N-acylanthranilic acids respectively with formamide and urethane, the latter has proved as effective a reagent as former. However, in the sense that condensations of 5- and 4-nitro-N-acetylanthranilic acids with urethane give the expected products in pure form while those of the same acids with formamide yield mixed products, urethane has proved a better reagent than formamide.

The condensations of N-acetylanthranilic acid and its 4- and 5-nitro or chloro derivatives with urea at 180–85° afforded the corresponding bz-unsubstituted, 7- and 6-nitro or

chlorine substituted-2 : 4-diketoquinazolines respectively. In fact the latter type of the compounds are formed when the corresponding anthranilic acids are condensed with urea⁽²⁾.

Surprisingly, however, the condensation of unsubstituted N-benzoylanthranilic acid and its 4- and 5-nitro and chloro derivatives with urea afforded the corresponding 2-Ph-3(H)-4-ketoquinazoline and its 7- and 6-nitro and chloro derivatives respectively. Further work in connection with the study of the condensation of N-substituted ureas and urethanes is deemed necessary for bringing out additional information about these condensations on the basis of which it may become possible to propose a satisfactory mechanism for the above mentioned reactions of urethane and urea. The work in this direction is in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL

4- and 5-nitro and chloro-N-acetyl and 4- and 5-chloro-N-benzoylanthranilic acids were prepared by the methods described for their syntheses in the preceding communication⁽¹⁾.

5-Nitro-N-benzoylanthranilic acid : A mixture of 5-nitroanthranilic acid (6 g.), benzoyl chloride (18 ml) and sodium hydroxide (10% : 105 ml) was stirred for a period of about twenty minutes when a large amount of yellowish solid separated out and the mixture became too viscous to be stirred. The solid was collected, washed with boiling water and crystallised from acetic acid in yellow needles m.p. 245–46°. Yield 50%. Found : N, 9.7. Calc. for $C_{14}H_{10}N_2O_5$: N, 9.8%.

4-Nitro-N-benzoylanthranilic acid : It was prepared by the method described above from 4-nitroanthranilic acid and was crystallised from acetic acid in yellow tiny needles, m.p. 250–51°⁽⁴⁾. Yield : 45%. Found : N, 9.7%. Calc. for $C_{14}H_{10}N_2O_5$: N, 9.8%.

4-Nitro-N-p-anisoylanthranilic acid : A solution of anisoylchloride (1.5 ml) in dry benzene (5 ml) containing a trace of pyridine was added to a suspension of finely powdered 4-nitroanthranilic acid (1 g.) in benzene (2 ml.) The mixture was refluxed for 4 hrs. and benzene was removed by distillation. The residual solid was washed with boiling water and crystallised from acetic acid in fine yellow needles, m.p. 258°. Found N: 8.6%. Calc. for $C_{15}H_{12}N_2O_6$: N, 8.8%. The 5- and 4-nitrosubstituted N-acylanthranilic acids described below were synthesised by this method using the required aroylchloride.

2. F. E. Sheibley, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1947, **12**, 743; N. A. Lange and F. E. Sheibley, *Org. Synth.*, 1948, Coll. Vol. II, 79.
3. S. Joshi and I. R. Gambhir, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, **26**, 3714.
4. Kyosuke Tsuda, Shigeru Fukushima, Hisao Ichakawa, Shoroku Yoshida and Genbei Ishii, *J. Pharm. Soc. Japan*, 1942, **62**, 69–77.

5-Nitro-N-p-anisoylanthranilic acid : It was crystallised from acetic acid in yellow needles, m.p. 235–36°. Found : N, 8.7%. Calc. for $C_{15}H_{12}N_2O_6$: N, 8.8%.

4-Nitro-N-p-nitrobenzoylanthranilic acid : It was crystallised from acetic acid in yellow small pellets, m.p. 293–94°. Found : N, 12.6%. Calc. for $C_{14}H_9N_3O_7$: N, 12.7%.

5-Nitro-N-p-nitrobenzoylanthranilic acid : It was crystallised from acetic acid in yellow flakes, m.p. 239°. Found : N, 12.8%. Calc. for $C_{14}H_9N_3O_7$: N, 12.7%.

Condensation of 4-nitro-N-acetylanthranilic acid with formamide : A mixture of 4-nitro-N-acetylanthranilic acid (1 mole) and formamide (3 mole) was heated at 180–85°. The solid product was suspended and stirred in bicarbonate solution, filtered and washed. It was crystallised from acetic acid. The product melted over a range from 265 to 275°. Repeated crystallisations could not bring about any change in the nature of the product. The UV spectral data of this product and those of 7-nitro-2(H)-3(H)-4-ketoquinazoline m.p. 275–76°; and its 2-methyl homologue m.p. 287⁽⁶⁾ indicated that the product was a mixture of above mentioned compound. The mixed product showed λ_{max} 252 (log $\epsilon = 2.01$) and 340 (1.141) $m\mu$. (The term in parenthesis indicates % absorption); 7-nitro-2(H)-3(H)-4-ketoquinazoline showed λ_{max} 252 (2.012), 340 (1.141) $m\mu$; 7-nitro-2-methyl-3(H)-4-ketoquinazoline showed λ_{max} 250 (2.024) and 343 (1.142) $m\mu$.

Condensation of 5-nitro-N-acetylanthranilic acid with formamide : This reaction when effected as described above afforded a product melting over a range 275–285° which was probably a mixture of 6-nitro-2-methyl-3(H)⁽⁶⁾ (m.p. 295°) and 2(H)-3(H) (m.p. 285–86°)⁽⁴⁾-4-ketoquinazolines. It showed λ_{max} 256 (1.590) and 324 (1.556) $m\mu$. 6-Nitro-2(H)-3(H) showed λ_{max} 253 (1.57) and 323 (1.54) $m\mu$, and its 2-methyl homologue showed λ_{max} 258–60 (s) (1.58) and 320 (1.729) $m\mu$.

Condensation of 4-nitro-N-acetylanthranilic acid with acetamide : Formation of 7-nitro-2-methyl-3(H)-4-ketoquinazoline : The above acid (1 mole) and acetamide (2.2 mole) were mixed and heated at 180–85° for 3 hrs. The product obtained after bicarbonate-treatment was crystallised from acetic acid in small yellow needles, m.p. 287–88°⁽⁵⁾. Yield : 50%. Found : N, 20.2%. Calc. for $C_9H_7N_3O_3$: N, 20.5%.

Condensation of 5-nitro-N-acetylanthranilic acid with acetamide : Formation of 6-nitro-2-methyl-3(H)-4-ketoquinazoline : This reaction was carried out as described above. The solid product was crystallised from acetic acid in fine yellow needles, m.p. 295°⁽⁷⁾. Yield : 50%. Found : N, 20.1%. Calc. for $C_9H_7N_3O_3$: N, 20.5%.

Condensation of 4-nitro-N-benzoylanthranilic acid with formamide : Formation of 7-nitro-2-phenyl-3(H)-4-ketoquinazoline : A mixture of 4-nitro-N-benzoylanthranilic acid (1 mole) and formamide (5 mole) was heated at about 180–85° for 3 hrs. The residual solid was suspended and stirred in bicarbonate solution, filtered and washed with water. It was

5. M. T. Bogert and H. S. Steiner, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, **27**, 330; M. T. Bogert and S. Klaber, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, **30**, 809.
6. A. J. Tomisek and B. E. Christensen, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 2423–5; M. T. Bogert and Cook, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1906, **28**, 1451.
7. E. C. Taylor, R. J. Knopf and A. L. Borrer, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **82**, 3152–7.

TABLE I
 Percent yield of 2(R)-3(H)-6(R₁)-7(R₂)-4-ketoquinazoline on condensation of 4(R₂)-5(R₁)-N(R-CO) anthranilic acid (1 mole) respectively with urethane (5 moles) and urea (3 moles) and formamide (3 moles)

$ \begin{array}{c} \text{R}_1 \\ \\ \text{C}_6\text{H}_3 \\ \\ \text{C}=\text{O} \\ \\ \text{OH} \\ \text{NH-C-R} \\ \\ \text{O} \end{array} \xrightarrow{\text{R}^1\text{-C-NH}_2} \begin{array}{c} \text{R}_1 \\ \\ \text{C}_6\text{H}_3 \\ \\ \text{NH} \\ \\ \text{R} \end{array} + \text{H} $		$ \begin{array}{c} \text{R}_1 \\ \\ \text{C}_6\text{H}_3 \\ \\ \text{NH} \\ \\ \text{R} \end{array} $		$ \begin{array}{c} \text{R}_1 \\ \\ \text{C}_6\text{H}_3 \\ \\ \text{NH} \\ \\ \text{R} \end{array} $		$ \begin{array}{c} \text{R}_1 \\ \\ \text{C}_6\text{H}_3 \\ \\ \text{NH} \\ \\ \text{R} \end{array} $		$ \begin{array}{c} \text{R}_1 \\ \\ \text{C}_6\text{H}_3 \\ \\ \text{NH} \\ \\ \text{R} \end{array} $		$ \begin{array}{c} \text{R}_1 \\ \\ \text{C}_6\text{H}_3 \\ \\ \text{NH} \\ \\ \text{R} \end{array} $	
R	R ₁	R ₂	With Formamide	With Urethane	With Urea	m.p. °C	Formula	Found	Calculated for	% Nitrogen	
N-benzoyl An.	Ph	H	63 ^(a)	82	56	238-40	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ N ₂ O	12.7	12.6		
4-Nitro-N-benzoyl An.	Ph	NO ₂	65	57	41	330-34	C ₁₄ H ₉ N ₃ O ₃	15.5	15.7		
5-Nitro-N-benzoyl An.	Ph	NO ₂	64	53	37	305-08	C ₁₄ H ₉ N ₃ O ₃	15.8	15.7		
4-Chloro-N-benzoyl An.	Ph	H	65 ^(a)	64	52	296-98	C ₁₄ H ₉ N ₂ OCl	11.0	10.9		
5-Chloro-N-benzoyl An.	Ph	Cl	66 ^(a)	66	43	280-82	C ₁₄ H ₉ N ₂ OCl	11.1	10.9		
N-Acetyl An.	Me	H	83 ^(a)	53 (74 at 210°)	a**	242-43	C ₉ H ₇ N ₂ O	17.3	17.5		
4-Nitro-N-acetyl An.	Me	H	NO ₂	58	b**	287-88	C ₉ H ₇ N ₃ O ₃	20.2	20.5		
5-Nitro-N-acetyl An.	Me	NO ₂	mix*	60	c**	295	C ₉ H ₇ N ₃ O ₃	20.1	20.5		
4-Chloro-N-acetyl An.	Me	H	79 ^(a)	71	d**	262-63	C ₉ H ₇ N ₂ OCl	14.2	14.4		
5-Chloro-N-acetyl An.	Me	Cl	78 ^(a)	74	e**	282-84	C ₉ H ₇ N ₂ OCl	14.1	14.4		

* Vide experimental.

** Products formed were 2 : 4-diketo-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroquinazoline derivatives : (a) 2 : 4-diketo-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroquinazoline, m.p. above 350°(a); (b) 7-nitroderivative, m.p. 338-40° (dec)^(e); (c) 6-nitroderivative, m.p. 330-32°(e); (d) 7-chloro derivative m.p. above 340°(e); (e) 6-chloro derivative, m.p. 321-25°(a).

crystallised from acetic acid in tiny yellow needles, m.p. 332–34°. Yield 65%. Reported m.p. 329°⁽³⁾. Found : N, 15.4%; Calc. for $C_{14}H_9N_3O_3$; N, 15.7%. Following this procedure the below-mentioned 6- and 7-nitro-2-aryl-3(H)-4-ketoquinazolines were prepared.

7-Nitro-2-p-nitrophenyl-3(H)-4-ketoquinazoline was formed from 4-nitro-N-p-nitrobenzoyl anthranilic acid. It was crystallised from acetic acid in brown powder, m.p. above 350°. Yield 62%. Found : N, 17.6%. Calc. for $C_{14}H_8N_4O_5$; N, 17.9%.

7-Nitro-2-p-anisoyl-3(H)-4-ketoquinazoline was crystallised from acetic acid in yellow needles, m.p. 340–42° (dec.). Yield 58%. Found : N, 14.2%. Calc. for $C_{15}H_{11}N_3O_4$; N, 14.1%.

6-Nitro-2-phenyl-3(H)-4-ketoquinazoline was crystallised from acetic acid in pale yellow needles, m.p. 303–04°. Yield 64%. Found : N, 15.9%. Calc. for $C_{14}H_9N_3O_3$; N, 15.7%.

6-Nitro-2-p-nitrophenyl-3(H)-4-ketoquinazoline was crystallised from acetic acid in brown powder m.p. 315–16° (dec.). Yield 62%. Reported m.p. 317–18°⁽⁷⁾. Found : N, 17.9%. Calc. for $C_{14}H_8N_4O_5$; N, 17.9%.

6-Nitro-2-p-anisoyl-3(H)-4-ketoquinazoline was crystallised from acetic acid in yellow needles, m.p. 235–36°. Yield 61%. Found : N, 14.4%. Calc. for $C_{15}H_{11}N_3O_3$; N, 14.1%.

Condensation of 4-nitroanthranilic acid with benzamide : Formation of (i) 7-nitro-2-phenyl-3(H)-4-ketoquinazoline, (ii) m-nitro benzanilide and (iii) 4-nitro-N-benzoyl anthranilic acid : This condensation was effected at 190° for 3 hrs. The solid obtained after treating the reaction mixture with bicarbonate solution was crystallised from alcohol in small yellow needles in very trace amount, m.p. 330–34°. It did not depress the melting point of the known sample on admixture. The mother liquor left after removal of 7-nitro-2-phenyl-3(H)-4-ketoquinazoline was diluted with water. The solid product was collected. It was found to be *m*-nitrobenzanilide (m.p. 157–58°). 4-Nitro-N-benzoylanthranilic acid was obtained from the bicarbonate extract.

Condensation of 5-nitroanthranilic acid with benzamide : Formation of (i) 6-nitro-2-phenyl-3(H)-4-ketoquinazoline, (ii) p-nitro benzanilide, (iii) 5-nitro-N-benzoylanthranilic acid : 6-Nitro-2-phenyl-3(H)-4-ketoquinazoline was obtained in yellow needles in trace amount (m.p. 305.8°). *p*-Nitrobenzanilide (m.p. 199–200°) and 5-nitro-N-benzoylanthranilic acid were obtained as described above.

General method for the condensation of N-acyl-anthranilic acid with urethane or urea : 4- or 5-nitro or chlorosubstituted N-acetyl or N-benzoyl anthranilic acid (1 mole) was heated with urethane (5 moles) or urea (3 moles) at 180–85° for 3 hrs. The cooled mixture was powdered and treated with bicarbonate solution, filtered and washed with water. The solid was collected and crystallised from ethanol. The yield and the properties of the compounds formed are reported in Table 1.

Department of Chemistry,
Sardar Patel University,
Ballav Vidyanagar.

Received November 9, 1968.

8. M. T. Bogert and G. Scatchard, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, **41**, 2055.
9. E. H. Huntress and J. V. K. Gladding, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, **64**, 2644.
10. R. L. McKee, M. K. McKee and R. W. Bost, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 940-2.